

Dissemination and communication package – From M1 to M30

Deliverable D7.2

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D7.2 Dissemination and communication package – From M1 to M30

<p>Deliverable title</p> <p>Work Package</p> <p>Lead beneficiary</p> <p>Due Date</p> <p>Actual delivery date</p> <p>Dissemination level</p> <p>Abstract</p> <p>Project Acronym</p> <p>Project Call</p> <p>Type of Action</p> <p>Project Start Date</p> <p>Project duration</p> <p>Grant Number</p>	<p>Dissemination and communication package – From M1 to M30</p> <p>WP7</p> <p>EUCORE</p> <p>Month 18 + update until Month 30</p> <p>29/03/2024 – Update submitted on 01/04/2025</p> <p>Public</p> <p>D7.2 details the dissemination and communication activities carried out throughout the first reporting period of the CaLby2030 project, as described in Tasks 7.3 and 7.4. This deliverable will be updated in months 30 and 42.</p> <p>CaLby2030</p> <p>HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02-13</p> <p>HORIZON EUROPE - Research and Innovation Action</p> <p>01/10/2022</p> <p>42 months</p> <p>101075416</p>
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HISTORY OF CHANGES

VERSION	DATE	MODIFICATION	PREPARED BY (Main contributors)	APPROVED BY
1	29/03/2024	Initial version	EUCORE - Martina Fantini - Irene Liverani - Melisa Borre'	CSIC (all review Team) All Consortium
2	01/04/2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction: updated until M30 (March 2025) and inclusion of brochure translations. • Promotional material: Inclusion of Logo user manual (Annex 1) Update on brochure translations Update of Figure 12 Inclusion of poster (Fig. 15) and Overview presentation (Fig. 16) • Website: Figure 22 updated with the latest newsletters Several updates from M19-30. • Publications: The complete table was updated to show all final publications from M1 to M30. • Project Dissemination events: Addition of the First mid-term Dissemination Workshop and photo 27. • Participation in external events: Organization of events from M1 to M18 in chronological order. Addition of 2 events that were missing in months 16 and 17 Addition of new events from M19-M30. • Liaison activities: Addition of new activities from M19-M30 and photos 30 and 31. • Social Media: General updates until M30 and addition of figure 34. • Press releases and other mass media: Addition of new activities from M19-M30. • Newsletters: Addition of the last 2 editions. • Annex: Inclusion of Logo user Manual 	EUCORE • Martina Fantini • Irene Liverani • Melisa Borre'	CSIC (all review Team) All Consortium

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ACRONYMS USED TO IDENTIFY CONSORTIUM MEMBERS

Ref.	organisation	Acronym
B1	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC
B2	SUMITOMO SHI FW ENERGIA OY	SFW
AE2.1	SUMITOMO SHI FW ENERGI AKTIEBOLAG (affiliated to SFW)	SFW AB
AE2.2	SUMITOMO SHI FW ENERGIA POLSKA SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA	SFW EP
B3	UNIVERSITÄT STUTTGART	USTUTT
B4	SWERIM AB	SWERIM
B5	LAPPEENRANNAN-LAHDEN TEKNILLINEN YLIOPISTO LUT	LUT
B6	CARMEUSE TECHNOLOGIES	CARMEUSE
B7	LABORATORIO ENERGIA AMBIENTE PIACENZA	LEAP
AE7.1	POLITECNICO DI MILANO (affiliated to LEAP)	POLIMI
B8	ACCIONA INDUSTRIAL SA	ACCIONA
B9	IREN SPA	IREN
AE9.1	IREN AMBIENTE SPA (affiliated to IREN)	IRENAMB
B10	VDZ TECHNOLOGY GGMBH	VDZ-T
AE10.1	VDZ SERVICE GMBH (affiliated to VDZ TECHNOLOGY gGmbH)	VDZ-S
B11	THOMAS ZEMENT GMBH	THOMAS
B12	UNIVERSITATEA BABES BOLYAI	UBB
B13	EU CORE CONSULTING SRL	EUCORE
B14	STICHTING SKU UNIVERSITEIT	SKU
B15	ALLEIMA TUBE AB	ALLEIMA
B16	HULLERAS DEL NORTE SA	HUNOSA
B17	BARNA STEEL SA/ Celsa Group	CELSA
AP18	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UCL

1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is an update of the first version (submitted in M18) and compiles all dissemination and communication materials and activities completed from M1 until M30.

As far as the materials are concerned, this report includes the logo, promotional materials (such as brochure), templates, website structure, social media accounts, publications, press releases and newsletters. All of them have been produced by EUCORE (leader of WP7) with the support of CSIC (Coordinator and WP8 leader) and inputs from all the partners. These were written in English and the brochure has been translated into the consortium members languages: Italian, Spanish, German, Finnish, French, Swedish, Romanian and Dutch.

All the materials detailed in this document were produced in accordance with the procedures and project visual identity of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D7.1) submitted in M3.

In addition, this report presents a summary of all the activities performed: dissemination events where CaLby2030 participated, publications, communication activities, participation in external events and liaison activities.

The majority of the materials and activities were initially agreed in the project Grant Agreement and D7.1, nevertheless, to increase the opportunities of CaLby2030 diffusion, further promotional materials - not originally foreseen- were developed, these are stickers, business cards and postcards, among others.

As a result, the deliverable is a reflection of the work done by all project partners in support of WP7, since dissemination and communication are regarded as strategic activities to engage all the target groups relevant to CaLby2030: Research and scientific community, industrial stakeholders, policymakers, regulatory organizations, press and general public.

While this deliverable thoroughly outlines all the developed Dissemination & Communication materials, channels and events, its primary goal is to assemble a "communication package" featuring resources and a summary of outreach efforts. It does not serve as an assessment of these endeavors, as they have already been addressed in the Technical report (part B) of the first and second reporting periods (RP1 and RP2) which included KPIs and event participant numbers.

2 LOGO

The final logo (see figure 1) was selected by the consortium among several proposed options in November 2022 and it displays the acronym of the project "CaLby2030" with an arrow representing its main ambition: to reach by 2030 the decarbonisation of industrial processes with Calcium Looping technologies.

It has two versions: with and without pay-off namely "*Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping*", which is the core impact expected from the project implementation and it aims at:

- Explaining the acronym;
- Place CaLby2030 in energy-intensive industries field;
- Make clear of the environmental field of action: decarbonisation;
- Mention the core technology: Calcium Looping.

Figure 1_CaLby2030 Logo (with and without pay-off)

The logo must be used in all project outputs (e.g. brochure, roll-ups, infographics, newsletters, deliverables, social media, website, publications, and materials for internal and external events) according to the indications included in the Logo user manual (See Annex 1). The manual specifies the typography that needs to be used, the exact color Pantone, measures, and how to proceed with different background colors (see figure 2)

Figure 2_Procedures on how to use the Logo extracted form the Logo user manual

In addition to the logo, it is of the utmost importance that any project output intended for dissemination and communication (even if performed through electronic means) includes the EU emblem and following text:

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (Project name: CaLby2030; grant number: 101075416). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The project is also supported by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. The EU emblem can be displayed either with or without pay-off, as indicated in the figure to follow.

Figure 3_EU emblem

3 TEMPLATES

Three templates have been prepared following the visual identity of the project, in order to harmonise the way CaLby2030 is presented: Report, PowerPoint template and General report (either public or confidential):

Report: to be used mainly for public and sensitive deliverables

Figure 4_Report template

PowerPoint template: to be used for all project presentations.

Figure 5_Presentations template

General report: for presenting other types of documents not strictly related to the project, such as Policy briefs or liaison activities

Figure 6_General report template

4 PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

A series of promotional materials were designed during the first reporting period following the creation of the visual identity of the project with the aim of strengthening the impact of the CaLby2030 D&C campaigns. In particular: brochure, block notes, folder, post cards, business card, template for event's invitation, roll-up and stickers, as described below:

Flyer/Brochure

CaLby2030's brochure has been designed as a tri-fold with a measurement of A4 when closed and A3 when open. It describes the main project information, goals, technology, demonstration sites, structure of the consortium and contact details.

The English brochure has been made available to all project partners for download in either printable or web versions. Translations have been produced during the RP2 in 8 different languages with the help of the consortium: Italian, Spanish, German, Finnish, French, Swedish, Romanian and Dutch. They are available for download in the NAS repository and in the website.

Figure 7_Brochure front/ back and internal pages

Block notes

The block notes have been designed following the color palette of the project and they are available to be downloaded and printed in two versions, either blank or checkered:

Figure 8_Block Notes cover and internal pages

Folder

The folder, useful to be presented on conferences and events, includes all the partners logos and and summary of CaLby2030’s main information and goals.

Figure 9_Folder front and back

Post cards

Three different versions of postcards have been designed, the first one showing the demonstration site of the MAGNUS facility in Germany, the second one presenting “La Pereda” demonstration site in Spain and the third one giving a short explanation of the project.

Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping

Funded by the European Union
www.calby2030.eu
 info@calby2030.eu

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Do not throw on the ground. Do the separate collection to save the environment.

Figure 10_Postcards front and back

Business card

A business card has been created with the purpose of having a small presentation of the project in hand for every occasion. It includes the main information of CaLby2030, the QR code to the website and the logos of the social media accounts.

Figure 11_Business Card front and back

Template for event's invitation

A template for event's invitation has been designed in the [Canva platform](https://www.canva.com/). It is ready to be modified according to the event by adding other partners logos (in case of liaison activities), title of the event, photo, agenda, description and link. The template has been used for creating the invitation of the 2nd Women in CCUS workshop and the First Dissemination event hold in M18 (RP2).

Figure 12_Template for event's invitation, example of the invitation for the 2nd Women in CCUS workshop and the First Dissemination event

Roll-up

A roll-up, expected to be printed in a measure of 2 m tall and 80 cm wide has been produced. It includes the main information of the project, goals, technology, photos of the demonstrations sites, map of the consortium partners, website and social media accounts. It has been created to showcase the project at conference booths or onstage during external events.

Figure 13_Roll-up

Sticker set

A set of 3 stickers has been designed in order to be attached to small gadgets (like cups or bottles, to laptops, bicycles, windows, cars, etc.). They are a good way of promoting the project in other places apart from work/office.

Figure 14_Stickers (50x50, 60x40, 80x30)

Updates on the Promotional material from month 19 to month 30:

Poster

The poster was created with the idea of boosting brand recognition for both internal and external events. While the poster is available to be printed in a variety of dimensions, its primary aim is to ensure portability, whilst also striving for enhanced compactness and lightness in comparison to the project roll-up.

Fig. 15. CaLby's Poster

Overview presentation

This overview has been created to ensure a consistent and cohesive PowerPoint presentation for all partners to be used in meetings and conferences for introducing the project. It is not subject to additional authorisation from the consortium.

Fig. 16. CaLby's Overview presentation

5 WEBSITE

Calby2030's website (<https://www.calby2030.eu/>) has been launched in December 2022 (MS12) following the project's visual identity. It has been built upon Concipio platform, a content management system (CMS) and it offers a responsive access for tablets and smartphones.

The website is written entirely in English and it is regularly updated by EUCORE (main administrator of the website), with CSIC's support and with inputs from all partners. Specific arrangements have already been made to ensure that it will be kept updated after the project conclusion for at least five years.

CaLby2030 website has been structured along a public and a private area, whose contents are described in what follows:

PUBLIC AREA

- Homepage
- Project
 - Overview of the project
 - Objectives
 - Structure
 - Consortium
 - Demonstration sites
- News & Events
 - News
 - Events

- Social wall
- Resources
- Contact
- Newsletter

The homepage (Figure 16) displays a user-friendly access to all the sections, 3 rotating images of the demonstration sites, the main information of the project including the logos of all the partners, the Top News of the moment in a green bar, access to the newsletter subscription and contact information. It also provides the links to the project social media accounts (LinkedIn, Instagram and Twitter).

Figure 17_Homepage of the website

The Project section includes a thorough explanation of the project’s methodology, main goals, structure (explaining each Work package in depth), the composition of all the consortium including a map, a description of each partner and a link to their website and a brief description of the three demonstration sites.

Figure 18_Consortium and Structure sections of the website

All the main news and events of the project can be easily found within the News & Events section, which includes a Calendar to keep track of the important dates. Here, a Social wall is also displayed where all the posts related to CaLby2030 from the three different social media are presented in one page for a better view.

Figure 19_Social wall, News and Events section of the website

In the Resources section, all the public information is displayed and available for download, such as the latest public Deliverables, and the scientific and press publications. In addition, the viewer can access to the abstracts of the sensitive deliverables. It is important to mention that all the public contents of the CaLby2030 project are collected in the trusted repository “CaLby2030 Community” on Zenodo. Given that some files may be too large to be stored on the website, they are exclusively uploaded into Zenodo, with only a link provided on the corresponding page of the website.

Figure 20_Resources section

The Contact area allows stakeholders and general Public to interact with the consortium by giving the possibility to write a question/comment choosing between the different fields: Cement/ Steel/ WtE/ Policy/ CO₂ management/ Other.

Figure 21_Contact section

Lastly, the Newsletter section allows the visitors to download the previous newsletters and subscribe to receive the future ones.

Figure 22_Newsletter section

PARTNER AREA

The Partner Area, is exclusively accessible to consortium members with a username and password and it serves as a shared repository for the final documents of CaLby2030:

- Budget/Finances
- Dissemination & Communication materials: including the latest versions of the logo, promotional material, templates, consent forms

- Contracts: in particular Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement;
- Deliverables and Milestones: differentiating between approved, rejected and submitted
- EC reporting.
- Project meetings.

Figure 23_Partner Area of the website

Updates on the website from month 19 to month 30:

- **Project structure:** Each Work Package has been thoroughly described, including some photos and illustrations to make it easier to understand.
- **Consortium:** The description of partners has been completed
- **Top news section:** Has been updated periodically with the most important piece of news of the moment.
- **Events:** All relevant events have been included in the calendar.
- **Resources:** This section was updated with all public deliverables and publications, including the link to Zenodo repository.
- **Social wall:** Has been updated with the latest posts.
- **Partner Area:** Credentials to access have been distributed among the new partner's contacts and the area has been updated with the latest documents.

In addition, some new features have been included such as: the possibility to download the brochures and a section where other relevant projects related to CCUS in the industry are listed.

6 PUBLICATIONS

In the following table, all the consortium members contributions from month 1 to month 30 in scientific publications, conference proceedings, articles and policy briefs are summarized:

#	Date and partners involved	Type	Title and Authors	PID	Journal / Conference	Open Access
1	October 2022 CSIC	Conference proceedings	Advanced CO ₂ capture systems based on Calcium Looping for deep decarbonization of flue gases	https://zenodo.org/records/14999062	16th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies (GHGT-16)	YES
2	March 14-15 th , 2023 SFW, USTUTT, VDZ, THOMAS	Conference proceedings	“CaL based on CFBs as a CO ₂ Capture Technology for the Cement Industry Development Pathway in the CaLby2030 Project” Martin Haaf, Mohamed Magdeldin, Edgardo Coda, Felix Mangold, Marco Lindemann Lino, Jan Sklyaruk, Nicolae Pascal	N/A	9th High Temperature Solid Looping Cycles Network (HTSLCN) Meeting Piacenza, Italy	NO
3	April 27 th , 2023 UCL	Article in journal	“Multi-objective economic and environmental assessment for the preliminary design of CO ₂ transport pipelines” Francesco Zanobetti, Sergey Martynov, Valerio Cozzani, Haroun Mahgerefteh	https://zenodo.org/records/10489023	Journal of Cleaner Production	YES
4	June 2023 SFW, CSIC, HUNOSA	Extended abstract	“Calcium looping using CFB technology to achieve negative emissions in biomass-fired power plants” Arias B., Haaf M., Magdeldin M., Coda Zabetta E., Diego M., Lorenzo M., DelaLlera E., Abanades J.C.	N/A	31st European Biomass Conference & Exhibition. EUBCE 2023	NO
5	July 2023 SFW	Article	TECHNICAL REPORT - STATE OF THE ART: CCS TECHNOLOGIES 2023	https://zenodo.org/records/14999382	Global CCS Institute Publication	YES

6	December 2023 SFW	Article in journal	Cost-effective Carbon Capture Technologies with Added Value Revenue Streams <i>Edgardo, Coda, Mohamed Magdeldin, Martin Haaf</i>	N/A	vgbe energy journal	NO
7	7 th May 2024 SKU	Other	An analysis of the European Industrial Carbon Management Strategy consultation: Who makes the normative decisions? <i>Senni Maatta, Moises Covarrubias, Vincent de Gooyert</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14770832	SSRN	YES
8	29 th May 2024 SKU EUCORE	Other – Policy Brief	Policy Brief: Will carbon management take off in Europe? How to get both industry and society on board? Insights from an analysis of the European Commission's Industrial Carbon Management Strategy Call for Evidence submissions <i>Senni Maatta, Martina Fantini, Moises Covarrubias, Vincent de Gooyert</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/11383537	Zenodo	YES
9	21 st July 2024 LUT, CSIC	Conference proceedings	Modelling-based proof-of-concept for Ca(OH) ₂ -enhanced CO ₂ capture in a calcium looping process <i>Secomandi, M., Arias, B., Nikku, M., Myöhänen, K., Ritvanen, J.</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14671473	14th International Conference on Fluidized Bed Technology (CFB14)	YES
10	21 st July 2024 SFW, SWERIM, LUT	Conference proceedings	A DYNAMICALLY OPERATED DUAL CFB CAL TAILORED FOR CARBON CAPTURE OF FUTURE IRON & STEEL INDUSTRIES DEVELOPMENT AND MODEL INVESTIGATION <i>Ari Kettunen, Martin Haaf, Malin Blomqvist, Magnus Lundqvist, Eemeli Anetjärvi, Jouni Ritvanen</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14944890	CFB14	YES
11	21 st July 2024	Conference proceedings	CALCIUM LOOPING TO DECARBONIZE CO ₂ -INTENSE	https://zenodo.org/records/14944975	CFB14	YES

	SFW		INDUSTRIES WITH ADDED REVENUE STREAMS <i>Martin Haaf, Ari Kettunen, Edgardo Coda Zabetta</i>			
12	24th July 2024 CSIC	Article in journal	Pilot Testing of Calcium Looping at TRL7 with CO2 Capture Efficiencies toward 99% <i>Borja Arias, Yolanda Alvarez Criado, Alberto Méndez, Paula Marqués, I. Finca, and J. Carlos Abanades</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14770572	Special Issue – Energy & Fuels	YES
13	8 th September 2024 SKU	Other	Resistance to market interventionism: an analysis of the European industrial carbon management strategy consultation <i>Senni Maatta, Moises Covarrubias, Vincent de Gooyert</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/13837188	Taylor & Francis	YES
14	11 th November 2024 UCL	Conference proceedings	Tiered Multi-Objective Optimization of CO2 Transport for CCS <i>Thomas Hennequin, Diarmid Roberts, Rosalie van Zelm, Solomon F. Brown, Richard T.J. Porter, Haroun Mahgerefteh and Sergey B. Martynov</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14771056	17th Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies Conference 2024 (GHGT-17)	YES
15	December 2024 LUT, CSIC	Article in journal	A conceptual evaluation of the use of Ca(OH) ₂ for attaining carbon capture rates of 99% in the calcium looping process <i>Secomandi, M., Nikku, M., Arias, B., Ritvanen, J.</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14770989	GHGT-17	YES
16	17 th December 2024 Polimi, LEAP, Swerim	Conference proceedings	Calcium Looping for Decarbonizing Electric Arc Furnace Steelmaking with CCS: A Preliminary Analysis of the Role of Solid Storage <i>Nestor D. Montiel-Bohorquez, Edoardo De Lena, Maurizio Spinelli, Malin Blomqvist, Paul Cobden, Manuele Gatti, Matteo Carmelo Romano</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14771148	GHGT-17	YES

17	17 th December 2024 UCL	Conference proceedings	A Mixed-integer Linear Programming Model for Multi-modal CO ₂ Transport <i>Fengyuan Zhang; Elena Catalanotti; Sergey Martynov; Richard Porter and Haroun Mahgerefteh</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14891585	GHGT-17	YES
18	17 th December 2024 CSIC	Conference proceedings	Operation experience in a TRL7 Calcium Looping plant using biomass as a fuel in the oxy-fired circulating fluidised bed calciner <i>Borja Arias, Yolanda Alvarez Criado, Alberto Méndez, Paula Marqués, I. Finca, and J. Carlos Abanades</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14900648	GHGT-17	YES
19	6 th January 2025 UCL	Conference proceedings	Techno-economic analysis of CO ₂ conditioning and transport systems for off- shore shipping <i>Zhengyang Wang, Richard T.J. Porter, Fengyuan Zhang, and Haroun Mahgerefteh</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14891993	GHGT-17	YES
20	January 21 st 2025 SKU	Article in journal	A critical review of social scientific research on carbon capture and storage <i>Senni Maatta, & Vincent de Gooyert</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14710836	Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	YES
21	25 th February, 2025 LUT	Article in journal	Dataset on the conceptual evaluation of carbon capture rates using Ca(OH) ₂ in the calcium looping process <i>Secomandi, M., Myöhänen, K., Ritvanen, J.</i>	https://zenodo.org/records/14988288	Data in Brief	YES

7 PROJECT DISSEMINATION EVENTS

As agreed in the GA, CaLby2030 has organized 2 dissemination events during the first reporting period:

1) CaLby2030 virtual Launch event (MS13): the Coordinator, Carlos Abanades, presented CaLby2030 to the EERA JP of CCS on the 8th of December 2022 in Bochum (short report available in the Partner Area of the website).

The event included 10 different companies in the audience as external experts, 5 countries not represented in the consortium (Norway, France, Denmark, Czech Republic, Greece) and 5 typologies of entities involved (Industry, SME, Academia, Association, General Public).

Figure 24_ Presentation of CaLby2030 to the EERA JP of CCS

2) “2nd Women in CCUS workshop” (MS14): joint workshop co-organised with C4U project (G.A. No 884418) following the successful of the 1st workshop on this subject. This dissemination workshop held on the 28th of September, 2023 in hybrid configuration, aimed at promoting STEM subjects as a study and research path for young women through the direct experience of female scientists working in CCUS. The initiative was divided into two main sessions: i) Role models: Selected speakers sharing direct experiences with the aim of inspiring the audience and highlighting critical issues that can be improved for gender equality and ii) Technical discussion, aiming at detecting concrete tools and strategies for the future, as seen in the agenda below.

Workshop title: “2nd Women in CCUS”
Co-organized by CaLby2030 and C4U projects
28th September 2023
VENUE AND ADDRESS: Jernkontoret, Kungsträdgårdsgatan 10, 111 47 Stockholm
[LINK FOR ONLINE ACCESS](#)

Agenda
28th September, 2023

Time	Topic	Speaker
09:00 – 09:15	Welcome	Ida Heintz (chair) – CaLby2030 Carlos Abanades – CaLby2030
09:15 – 09:40	Gender dimension and gender equality in CCUS	CINEA, Maria MORAGUES Canova
09:40 – 09:55	Why ... in CCUS? – workshop introduction	Moja Persdotter, Vinnova
09:55 – 11:35	Role models, selected successful CCUS stories	Martina Fantini
09:55 – 10:05	Dorothee Reiböcher	Chair of the C4U Gender Balance, Equality and Ethics Board
10:05 – 10:15	Monisha Rastogi	TFL
10:15 – 10:25	Lis Blume	LiS BAUME
10:25 – 10:35	Andrés Ramirez	TU Delft
10:35 – 10:45	Carla Sapart	CO2 Hub Europe
10:45 – 10:55	Malin Blomqvist	SWERIM
10:55 – 11:05	Jens Kim	SINTEF
11:05 – 11:15	Maria Abzornote	Energy Company
11:15 – 11:25	Ariane Giraneza	BELLONIA
11:25 – 11:35	Hina Kuchova	CESP
11:35 – 12:00	Coffee break	
12:00 – 13:30	Technical discussion	
13:30 – 13:45	Wrap up and next steps	

Fig. 25_ Agenda of the Women in CCUS workshop

The workshop was hosted by SWERIM and organised by SWERIM, EUCORE and UCL. Public report, slides and recording are available in the [“CaLby2030 Community” in Zenodo](#).

Fig. 26_ Participants in presence in the 2nd Women in CCUS workshop

The event included 8 external speakers plus 7 in the audience, 2 countries not represented in the consortium (Norway and USA) and 6 typologies of entities involved (Academia, industry, NGO, SME, association and sole trader).

Dissemination events from month 19 to month 30:

On March 27th 2024, the **First mid-term Dissemination Workshop** of the “CaLby2030” project took place in Stuttgart, Germany, hosted by one of the partners, the University of Stuttgart -IFK (USTUTT).

With more than 30 participants in presence and 40 connected online, including consortium, relevant stakeholders from CaLby2030’s Industrial Advisory Council and general public, the event was divided into 3 main sessions: presentation of the results obtained in the first year and a half of the project, technical discussion and visit to University of Stuttgart’s MAGNUS Pilot plant, one of the three demonstration sites of the project. The event has been a success also because several external experts from outside the consortium have attended in person. The questions that were brought up by them were both interesting and valuable for the partners, which led to significant discussions among the audience.

Fig. 27: Photos of the First mid-term Dissemination Workshop

Take away messages, Public Slides, Agenda, Flyer and video available in our community in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/11198437> where, with 152 views and 597 downloads it is clear the significant impact of the event which played a key role in boosting visibility outside the consortium.

8 PARTICIPATION IN EXTERNAL EVENTS

The following table contains a summary of the partners' participation on external events from month 1 to 18:

#	Partners involved	Activity name & Description	Type of activity	Date	Location	Target audience reached.
1	CSIC	CaLby2030 presentation for companies	Conference	16/11/2022	Oviedo, Spain	Industry
2	CSIC	Presentation in Spanish CCS platform PTECO2	Meeting	23/11/2022	Madrid, Spain	Research communities

3	CSIC	Presentation to the EERA JP of CCS (Project Launch event)	Meeting	08/12/2022	Bochum, Germany	Research communities
4	CSIC	Presentation in CINEA Cluster meeting	Meeting	27/01/2023	Online	Research communities
5	CSIC	Carbon Capture Workshop by ANICA and AC ² OCem	Conference	08/03/2023	online	Research communities
6	CSIC/LEAP	Presentation of CaLby2030 project at 9th HTSLCM	Conference	14/03/2023	Piacenza, Italy	Research communities; Industry, business partners; Innovators; Investors
7	CSIC	Regional Infoday on Horizon Europe Cluster 5	Conference	02/05/2023	Gijón, Spain	Companies
8	CSIC	Innovación en la producción de energía limpia, segura y eficiente	Conference	02/05/2023	Avilés, Spain	Research communities
9	CSIC	CUCC Oviedo University	Conference	05/05/2023	Gijón, Spain	Research communities and policymakers
10	LEAP	Presentation of CaLby2030 project at IETS TCP's International Conference	Conference	10/05/2023	Gothenburg, Sweden	Research communities; Industry, business partners; Innovators; Investors
11	CSIC, SFW, HUNOSA	31st European Biomass Conference & Exhibition. EUBCE 2023	Conference	5-8/06/2023	Bologna, Italy	Research communities
12	LEAP	Presentation of CaLby2030 project at Mater Conference	Conference	06/06/2023	Piacenza, Italy	Research communities; Industry, business partners; Innovators; Investors
13	SKU (Radboud University)	Presentation for the Social CCS network.	Other scientific collaboration	21/06/2023	online	Research communities

14	CSIC	Summer courses University of Cantabria	Conference	05/07/2023	Cantabria, Spain	University students
15	CSIC	Ciceron itineraries	meeting	14/07/2023	Madrid, Spain	Research communities
16	SFW	Cemtech	Education and training event	06/09/2023	Online	Industrial, business partners
17	CSIC, HUNOSA	CSIC ciceron itineraries	talk	12/09/2023	Oviedo, Spain	Civil society & research communities
18	SFW	VGBE Congress	Conference	20-21/09/ 2023	Berlin, Germany	Research communities, Industry
19	SFW	Carbon CaptureTechnology Expo 2023	Conference	27-28/09/2023	Bremen, Germany	Industrial, business partners
20	SKU	Earth System Governance Conference	Conference	24/10/2023	Radboud University Nijmegen	Research communities
21	SKU, SWERIM	Participation in a roundtable at the C4U project event <i>Is societal trust the missing link for a policy and business case for carbon capture, utilisation and storage in a Net- Zero transition?</i>	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	24/01/2024	Brussels, Belgium.	Research communities
22	EUCORE, POLIMI	Meeting on research and business activities about ongoing CCUS projects in Emilia-Romagna region, Italy. Involving professors from UniBO, Polimi, Wyoming University and EUCORE.	Other scientific collaboration	15/02/2024	Bologna University, Italy	Research communities

In addition, there were 2 sites visits (to La Pereda and Luleå plants) hosted by CSIC/Hunosa and Swerim. The targeted KPI's were 15 participants or more, and both of the visits achieved and surpass the value with 33 and 35 participants respectively.

Updates on participation on external events from month 19 to month 30:

#	Partners involved	Activity name & Description	Type of activity	Date	Location	Target audience reached.
1	SFW, SWERIM, LUT, CSIC	Several presentations of CaLby2030 on the 14th International Conference on Fluidized Bed Technology (CFB14)	Conference	21-24/07/2024	Taiyuan, China	Research communities; Industry, business partners; Innovators; Investors
2	IREN, IREN AMBIENTE	Iren's CCUS Day - a workshop on CCUS and Iren's projects and plans for decarbonization	Education and training event	17/10/2024	Reggio Emilia, Italy	Industry (Iren's corporate staff and technical units)
3	UCL, CSIC, Polimi, LEAP, Swerim	Several Presentations of CaLby2030 on the 17th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies (GHGT-17)	Conference	20/10/2024	Calgary, Canada	Research communities; Industry, business partners; Innovators; Investors; International organisations (IEA); EU institutions
4	UCL	Presentations related to WP4 and WP5 on the UKCCSRC Knowledge Exchange Conference 2024	Conference	05/11/2024	Sheffield, UK	Research communities; Industry, business partners; National authorities (UK Department of Energy Security and Net Zero; UK Environment Agency)
5	SKU	Presentation in a Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) internal meeting, Advisory Council and IWG9 Plenary	Meeting	04/12/2024	Brussels, Belgium	Research communities, Industry, International organisations, EU institutions, other
6	CSIC	Presentation of CaLby2030 and results from la Pereda pilot in the "I FORO ANUAL DE LA CIENCIA, TECNOLOGÍA E INNOVACIÓN ENERGÉTICAS"	Conference	12/12/2024	Madrid, Spain	Research institutions, National Associations, Public Bodies, National authorities.

9 LIAISON ACTIVITIES

“Public perception and business models” joint event: CaLby2030, together with eCOCO2 (GA 838067), CLEANKER (GA 764816) and HERCCULES (GA 101096691) projects and the support of CINEA, has co-organized the event on “Public perception and business models” held in Brussels on November 14th, 2023.

Funded by the European Union	
14th November 2023, Brussels Rue du Trône 62, 1050 Ixelles, Belgium CSC Room 3, 7th floor	
Agenda	
9:00 - 9:30	Registration
9:30 - 9:35	Welcome and workshop overview: Jose Jofar, Martina Fontijn (on behalf of eCOCO2 & CLEANER/CALBY2030/HERCCULES)
9:35 - 9:40	CINEA Introduction Speaker - Maria Moraguer Canovas
Session 1: Public Perception	
Chair: Martina	
9:40 - 9:50	Case Study - CAU Speaker: Vincent de Gooijer
9:50 - 10:00	Case Study - ACCESS Speaker: Sanchez Bertraga, Jose Alberto
10:00 - 10:10	Case Study - CO2SAGES Speaker: Zoe Morrison
10:10 - 10:20	Case Study - CaLby2030 Speaker: Jose M. Serra
10:20 - 10:35	Case Study - PuriSTRATEGY and HERCCULES Speaker: Elisabeth Duetzschke
10:35 - 10:45	Case Study - eCOCO2 Speaker: Linda Engelmann
10:45 - 10:55	Case study - MOF4air Speaker: Spyros Kyriazas
10:55 - 11:30	Coffee Break
11:30 - 11:40	Case Study - Sun-To-X Speaker: Anne Pigeon
11:40 - 11:50	Case Study - 3D Speaker: Lebbe Troilo
11:50 - 12:05	Case Study - NEGEM and AURORA Speaker: Daniel Renner
12:05 - 12:15	Case Study - CO2SAMOS Speaker: Inke Hoyerlmper
12:15 - 12:25	Case Study - CO2Fokus Speaker: Adriana Diaz
12:25 - 12:40	Case Study - DigMon & BiNET Speaker: Danny Otto
12:40 - 12:55	Q&A
12:55 - 14:00	Lunch

Funded by the European Union	
Session 2: Business Models	
Chair: Jose	
14:00 - 14:10	Case study - CAU Speaker: Hannah Galbreath-Olive
14:10 - 14:20	Case study - GICO Speaker: Chino Lariro
14:20 - 14:30	Case study - 3D Speaker: Paulo Cousoy
14:30 - 14:40	Case Study - VIVALDI Speaker: Jorge Senan Salinas (BETA Technological Center) and Elvira Serra (Ade Utilities)
14:40 - 14:55	Q&A
14:55 - 15:15	Short Break
End-of-day summary	
Chair	
15:15 - 15:30	Summary of issues emerging in case studies for Session 1 Rapporteur: Elisabeth Duetzschke
15:30 - 15:45	Summary of issues emerging in case studies for Session 2 Rapporteur: Enrico Bassi
15:45 - 16:00	Formalization/agreeing on the major challenges Rapporteur: Laura Almar
16:00 - 16:10	Concluding remarks and greeting Speaker: Jose and Martina
16:10 - 16:45	Coffee Break
17:00	End

Figure 28_ Agenda of the “Public perception and Business Models Joint event”

With more than 20 selected Horizon 2020 & HE projects and more than 50 key stakeholders involved in the audience, the workshop represented a unique opportunity to strongly impact both on the activities still to be implemented by the ongoing projects and the design of new projects at higher TRL (close to commercial scale). Bringing together stakeholders from various technical projects represents an excellent networking opportunity facilitating collaboration, knowledge sharing, and future partnerships.

Figure 29_ "Public perception and Business Models Joint event" – Bruxelles, 14 November 2023

The targeted KPI's were 5 European Union projects or more, and the event met and exceeded the value, with 20 EU projects involved.

Updates on Liaison activities from month 19 to month 30:

1. As part of its liaison activities, CaLby2030 contributed to the evaluation of the circularity assessment methodologies for a project supported by CINEA aiming at validating LCA methodological approaches.
2. On February 26th and 27th, 2025, the **International Forum on Recent Cross-Cutting Developments in CCU/CCS** took place in the INCAR, CSIC premises in Oviedo, Spain. The event, organized by C4U and CaLby2030 projects and co-organized by HERCCULES, INITIATE, ConsenCUS,

ELECTRA, Encase and EMPHATICAL, delved into the multidisciplinary nature of current EU-funded research in Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage (CCU/CCS). The objective behind the event was to bring together many experts from numerous projects in order to share expertise, explore recent developments and discuss the current challenges on the industry and its related technologies, thus making it a private event exclusively held to enhance knowledge in the research community. A page at the C02 Value Europe site has been opened, where there is the possibility to download the agenda and the blog of the event including the session highlights and photos (<https://co2value.eu/conference-ccu-ccs-oviedo/>).

Figure 30_Flyer of the Oviedo International Forum and first page of the Blog

Figure 31_Photos of the Oviedo International Forum

10 SOCIAL MEDIA

Three social media accounts have been created: LinkedIn (@CaLby2030 project), Twitter (@CaLby2030) and Instagram (@CaLby2030), to connect with general public, stakeholders and disseminate news about the project. Twitter and Instagram were opened in M2 and LinkedIn in M3, and eachone has different aims/targets:

- LinkedIn is much more oriented towards professional content and it can be used to establish networks on specific topics
- Instagram acts mainly as a repository for images and audio-visual content
- Twitter allows to engage in real-time bidirectional communication with the community and is preferably used to share instant announcements, industry news, comments, opinions, blog content, visual content (such as infographics), news on recent and future events and general tips.

A thorough description of expected number of characters and target audience of each account is detailed on the D&C plan (D7.1).

Figure 32_CaLby2030 social accounts

Posts are expected to be different in each of the accounts, while on LinkedIn we normally post description of the sites/ specific equipment, hiring positions, results/publications or graphics/simulations about the activities, Instagram is more focused on photos of the current team, new entries, videos or reels explaining the activities and photos about participation in conferences or presentations. Twitter on the other hand, is mostly use for sharing instant content such as CaLby2030 participation in conferences or other event.

EUCORE is in charge of the overall management of the Social accounts by collecting contributions from all the beneficiaries according to the editorial plan agreed with the consortium (see Annex 2 of the D7.1). The contributions are then transformed with the visual identity of the project and posted.

In addition to this, all partners actively contribute by liking the posts, leaving comments, and reposting on their social accounts.

Figure 33_Examples of LinkedIn posts published during the first reporting period

Throughout month 19 up until month 30, the Editorial Plan has been successfully implemented and has resulted in a growth in posts and followers across all platforms that the CaLby2030 project uses to divulge updates and information on its development. Nevertheless, despite considerable efforts to increase the number of posts, the X (former Twitter) channel persists with poor outcomes in terms of user engagement. Consequently, in the upcoming months, consideration will be given on to how to enhance its effectiveness and/or explore potential alternatives.

CaLby’s social media channels have reached a variety of communities spanning from civil society to industry and research communities. The following figures summarizes the growth of the Editorial Plan by social media platform:

- **LinkedIn:** a +47% growth in followers and a +10% growth in interactions, with a total of 56 posts.
- **Instagram:** a +18% growth in followers and a +10% growth in interactions, with a total of 45 posts.
- **Twitter (X):** a +18% growth in followers with a total of 52 posts.

Figure 34_Examples of posts published during months 19 to 30.

11 PRESS RELEASES AND OTHER MASS MEDIA

The table below provides a summary of all the communication activities carried out within months 1 to 18, including: press releases, articles, social media posts (outside the CaLby2030 accounts), mentions on websites, participation on events and appearances on Youtube and television.

#	Activity name	Description	Date	Communication channel	Target audience reached
1	"CaLby2030 for companies" Launch event MS13	LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram post from INNOVASTURIAS (local companies association and organizer of this event) for the presentation of "CaLby2030 for companies" Launch event MS13	11/11/2022	Social_Media	Industry, business partners
2	Launch event MS13	Twitter post from INCAR -CSIC for the presentation of "CaLby2030 for companies"	14/11/2022	Social_Media	Industry, business partners
3	Launch event MS13	Website event announcement from CDTi (national level R&D companies granting authority) for the presentation of "CaLby2030 for companies"	14/11/2022	Website	Industry, business partners
4	Launch event MS13	Website video announcement from INNOVASTURIAS after "CaLby2030 for companies" Launch event MS13	14/11/2022	Website	Industry, business partners
5	Launch event MS13	Recorded video from the event on youtube's INNOVASTURIAS account after the launch event	25/11/2022	Video	Industry, business partners

6	Launch event MS13	Twitter post from the Chamber of Commerce of Oviedo covering the brief introduction in the event of its president Carlos Panicerres after "CaLby2030 for companies" Launch event MS13	16/11/2022	Social_Media	Industry, business partners
7	Launch event MS13	Event post in the CSIC Asturian Deputy for "CaLby2030 for companies" Launch event MS13	16/11/2022	Website	Industry, business partners
8	Launch event MS13	Press news mentioning CaLby2030 in Spanish local newspaper "La Nueva España"	13/11/2022	Media_Article	Civil society
9	Launch event MS13	Press release describing the project, published on CSIC front page (main website)	23/11/2022	Press_Release + Website	Civil society
10	Launch event MS13	Press news dedicated to CaLby2030 in local newspaper "La Nueva España"	23/11/2022	Media_Article	Civil society
11	Launch event MS13	Press news dedicated to CaLby2030 in regional newspaper "El diario de León"	23/11/2022	Media_Article	Civil society
12	Launch event MS13	Press new dedicated to CaLby2030 in "Interempresas" online newspaper	23/11/2022	Media_Article	Industry, business partners
13	Launch event MS13	CaLby2030 post in INCAR-CSIC website front page	23/11/2022	Website	Civil society
14	SFW News	"Sumitomo SHI FW demonstrates capturing carbon emissions for steel, cement and power" - LinkedIn post on SFW account	05/01/2023	Social_Media	Industry, business partners
15	SFW News	Sumitomo SHI FW demonstrates capturing carbon emissions for steel, cement and power News at the company's web site	05/01/2023	Website	Civil society
16	Bio360Expo - Nantes, France	SFW - Speaker's slot + booth in the Bio360Expo at Nantes, France + LinkedIn post	08-09/02/2023	Event + Social_Media	Industry, business partners
17	"La Nueva España" newspaper	Press interview to CSIC's Asturian Institutional delegate mentioning CaLby2030 + 2 Press news about HUNOSA power plant retrofit mentioning CaLby2030 and one interview to HUNOSA	12/2023	Media_Article	Civil society
18	Prof. Consonni's speech	Speech of Prof. Consonni at the IREN anniversary in Torino (Italy) + news on IREN's website	10/05/2023	Event + Social_Media	Industry, business partners
19	Earth Day	Earth Day - Highlighting CaLby2030 - SFW - LinkedIn post	24/04/2023	Social_Media	Industry, business partners
20	First SAC meeting	Twitter post about the first SAC meeting	10/04/2023	Social_Media	Civil society
21	"El Comercio" newspaper	Press releases about 2 events: 1) Regional Infoday on Horizon Europe Cluster 5 and 2) Innovación en la producción de energía limpia, segura y eficiente	02/05/2023	Press_Release	Civil society
22	News on company web page	News at UBB's company web page (Department and faculty website) - "International projects with the Department of Chemical Engineering"	31/05/2023	Website	Industry, business partners
23	Investigadores del CSIC abordan el	"Investigadores del CSIC abordan el reto de la energía verde" - Mention of CaLby2030 project and	14/07/2023	Website	Civil society

	reto de la energía verde	its technologies with other green technologies on CSIC's website			
24	Cicerón 3.5	CSIC - "Cicerón 3.5 - "La descarbonización industrial mediante captura de CO2" – Youtube Video of J.C. Abanades showing la Pereda pilot and the project technologies	14/07/2023	Video	Civil society
25	University of Cantabria summer course	News at University of Cantabria's website for summer courses including a presentation of CaLby2030, targeting students	03/07/2023	Website	Civil society
26	CaLby2030 in TVE (Spanish national television)	Interview in TVE (Spanish national television) showing INCAR facilities and CaLBY2030 Roll-up	12/09/2023	TV/Radio campaign	Civil society
27	SFW article	"SFW's networked R&D drives global decarbonization development" - Mention of CaLby2030 project in an article on SFW's website	06/11/2023	Media_Article +Website	Industry, business partners
28	SFW article	"SFW's networked R&D drives global decarbonization development" - Mention of CaLby2030 project in an article + Post on Social Media (Linkedin, Facebook and Twitter)	06/11/2023	Media_Article + Social_Media	Civil society
29	Article in RIENERGIA magazine	CaLby2030 - Calcium Looping to capture CO2 from industrial processes by 2030" - Martina Fantini, J. Carlos Abanades, M ^a Elena Diego	05/2023	Media_Article	Industry, business partners
30	CINEA Joint Event on Public Perception and Business models	Talk on public perception from Jose Luis Oviedo (ICMAN-CSIC) about social acceptance study in CaLby2030	14/11/2023	Event + Social_Media	EU institutions
31	2nd "Women in CCUS" workshop	2nd "Women in CCUS" workshop	28/09/2023	Event + Social_Media	Industry, business partners
32	CO2 Value Europe	Mention of CaLby2030 on CO2 Value Europe's website		Website	Industry, business partners
33	Enlit	Mention of CaLby2030 on Enlit's website		Website	Industry, business partners
34	Hirecord project	Mention of CaLby2030 on Hirecord website		Website	Industry, business partners

29 - Article in RiENERGIA magazine: A collaborative article named: "*CaLby2030: per catturare la CO₂ dai processi industriali entro il 2030*" was published in RiENERGIA magazine and is available both in the [CaLby2030 Community on Zenodo](#) and on [Staffettaonline webjournal](#). The translation of the article is available upon request.

Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping

Figure 35_RiEnergia article

32 - CO₂ Value Europe

All 3 CaLby2030 demonstration sites have been included in the CCU projects database of the CO₂ Value Europe website. <https://database.co2value.eu/projects/322>

Figure 36_CaLby2030 in CO2 Value Europe website

33 - Enlit

CaLby2030 has been included in the Projects Directory of the Enlit website. <https://www.enlit.world/projects/calby2030/>

Figure 37_CaLby2030 in Enlit website

34 – Hirecord project

The project “Scaling-up of a highly modular rotating packed bed plant with an efficient solvent for capture cost reduction” (acronym: Hirecord), which was funded under the same call as CaLby2030 (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02-13), mentioned CaLby2030 in their directory of Industrial CCUS Projects.

Figure 38_CaLby2030 in HIRECORD website

Updates on Press Releases and other Mass Media from month 19 to month 30:

#	Activity name	Description	Date	Communication channel	Target audience reached
35	Interview	CSIC_Interview in La Nueva España local Spanish newspaper on the CaLby2030 project	14/02/24	Media_Article	Civil Society
36	Article	CSIC_Article on the project in the Spanish newspaper El diario de León	24/04/24	Media Article	Civil Society
37	LinkedIn Post	LUT_LinkedIn post on CaLby2030's participation in HCD2024	04/24	Social Media	Research communities

38	LinkedIn Post	CSIC_Social Advisory Board Meeting post on LinkedIn	18/06/24	Social Media	Research communities
39	LinkedIn Post	UCL_17th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies (GHGT-17)	20/10/24	Social Media	Research Communities
40	Twitter Post	UCL_17th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies (GHGT-17)	20/10/24	Social Media	Research Communities
41	LinkedIn Post	LUT_17th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies (GHGT-17)	10/24	Social Media	Research Communities
42	Interview	CSIC_20 min interview on Canal sur Radio covering a detailed explanation of CCUS as a crucial mitigation measure of climate change	01/11/24	Radio	Civil Society
43	Press Release	LUT_Press release in Finnish on the project	06/11/24	Media Article	Civil Society
44	Article	CSIC_Article in "El Pais" newspaper covering the topic of CCUS and including input from Carlos Abanades	10/11/24	Media Article	Civil Society
45	LinkedIn	LUT_Post on a CaLby2030 research publication	11/24	Social Media	Research Communities
46	Video	IREN_Article and video on Iren's intranet reporting the activities carried out during the CCUS Day	18/11/24	Video	Industry, business partners

12 NEWSLETTERS

Newsletters are planned on a bi-annual basis, as agreed on the GA. The first one was distributed on March 2023 providing a **summary of the activities performed** during the first months of the project. It starts with a summary of the kick-off meeting and first General Assembly, held in Oviedo, Spain in October 2022, including a visit to "La Pereda" pilot plant. Then describes **CaLby2030's participation in events**, in particular, the 9th HTSLCN meeting and final CLEANKER conference held in Piacenza, Italy in March 2023. **Lastly, the "where we are" section** details the deliverables and milestones submitted and a brief description of the coming events.

The second newsletter was finalised and sent in November 2023. Following the same structure, it includes a summary of the events attended by CaLby2030 within that period, namely:

- 31st European Biomass Conference & Exhibition. EUBCE 2023, 5-8 June, Bologna, Italy
- The 12th Trondheim Conference on CO₂ Capture, Transport and Storage, TCCS12, June 19 - 21, 2023
- 2nd Women in CCUS Workshop (28th September 2023)
- Joint event on "Public Perception and Business Models" (Bruxelles, 14 November 2023)

And a detailed description of the 2nd General Assembly and 3rd Executive Board Meetings held in Sandviken, Sweden in September 2023, including a visit to Alleima facilities. In addition, this

newsletter included a brief summary of “where we are” on each WP with vibrant photos to illustrate each point.

Both of the newsletters are available to be downloaded from the [website](#).

Fig. 39_ Template of the newsletter

Figure 40_ First pages of Newsletters 1 and 2

Updates on Newsletters from month 19 to month 30:

Two newsletters have been produced within these months:

- **Newsletter 3:** This edition was delivered in July 2024 and included as main events/activities the following:
 - Joint event on “Public Perception and Business Models”, held in Brussels, Belgium, on November 14th 2023.
 - The First mid-term dissemination Workshop and 2nd Advisory Council Meeting held in Stuttgart, Germany on March 27th 2024.
 - The Policy Brief entitled: Will carbon management take off in Europe? How to get both industry and society on board?

- **Newsletter 4:** The fourth edition was released on February 2025 being the most important piece of news:
 - The 3rd General Assembly and 6th Executive Board Meetings held in Lappeenranta, Finland on August 28th and 29th 2024 and the Workshop on Societal readiness of CCUS technologies: *CCUS expert perceptions of the enablers and barriers*”, by Radboud University done on August 29th , 2024.
 - CaLby2030’s presentations on the GHGT conference 2024, held in Alberta, Canada on October 20th - 24th, 2024
 - All the lasted publications uploaded in the Zenodo repository.

13 ANNEX

Logo user manual

CaLby2030

Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping

CaLby2030 _ Manuale d'uso

FEBBRAIO 2023

CaLby2030 (HoratioDBol)

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12) Cantami, o Diva, del Pelide Achille

18) Cantami, o Diva, del Pelide Achille

24) Cantami, o Diva, del Pelide Achille

36) Cantami, o Diva, del Pelide Achille

48) Cantami, o Diva, del Pelide Achille

Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping (Segoe UI)

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12) Cantami, o Diva, del Pelide Achille

18) Cantami, o Diva, del Pelide Achille

24) Cantami, o Diva, del Pelide Achille

36) Cantami, o Diva, del Pelide Achille

48) Cantami, o Diva, del Pelide Achille

Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping

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CaLby2030

Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping

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